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Governance and Politics: The Nigerian Baptists' Perspective on Governance in Nigeria

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Abstract

Baptist is a term describing a Christian belonging to a Baptist church or a Baptist denomination. The name is derived from a conviction that followers of Jesus Christ are commanded to be baptised (through water immersion) to show the public display of their belief in Christ Jesus. Meanwhile, the Nigerian Baptist Convention is one of the most prominent denominations in Nigeria today, and it originated from a foreign mission of the Southern Baptist Convention of the United States of America. It is on this note that this paper investigates the Nigerian Baptists' contributions to Nigeria's politics and governance and it also assesses the roles and contributions to the nation-building in Nigeria. In addition, with the theory of secularism, oral data collection, and historical, descriptive, and case study designs, the article appraises the Nigerian Baptist Convention's influence on governance and politics in Nigeria. The paper's finding is that though the Nigerian Baptists have contributed so much to the political system in Nigeria through education, health, social services, employment, and agriculture among many others, there is still work to be done. The article among many others suggests how the Nigerian Baptists can have more influence in Nigerian politics. The paper especially recommended that the Baptists in Nigeria need to sell themselves to the society politically. The article's final submission is that the

Nigerian Baptists' leadership needs to be more vocal and it also needs to increase its political presence through expression of its political views on trending national issues.

Keywords: Governance, politics, the Nigerian Baptist Conventions, secularist theory

Introduction

Politics is a product of social relations. Anyone who cannot relate to others cannot practice politics successfully. Politics is about power play. One basic thing that politicians seek in politics is power. What power is seen in governance? If a closer look is given to the Baptist practices, it is evidence that politics established Baptists. Politics is all about who leads the Baptist institutions. According to the Nigerian Baptists' principle, the majority carries the day, that is democracy. Therefore, from this aforementioned, the Baptists should be the best in politics. They should be good politicians because they have been prepared for politics from their childhood to when they become adults.

Based on this premise, the work assessed the Baptists' perspectives on politics and the church's roles and contributions to the political system and governance in Nigeria. The objective of this research is to identify the strong areas where the Baptists in Nigeria have contributed immensely to nation-building and also to point out the weak areas where the church remains aloof. The findings of this work are that the Baptists have performed below the expected standard in participation in politics. The findings also show that the Baptists took the policy that "we are in the world but not of the world" (1 John 2:15-17) literally and too seriously. The Nigerian Baptists interpreted it just too loosely and literally. They got it with a wrong understanding of what the Scripture is preaching. Even Jesus Christ did not preach abandonment of secular authority. He wanted us to obey it. Meanwhile, the interpretation by the Baptists shows their ignorance of the significance and roles of a state and its citizens.

According to Professor J. A. Ayoade in an oral interview, membership of a state is compulsory for any residence of a state. A state has an inclusive and overreaching authority over anybody who resides in a state. Membership of a state is not optional. So far, for anybody to opt out of a state, is to deny himself of rights and privileges that are guaranteed by the state and that only the state can offer. So, opting out of the state makes anybody a loser.

It is on this note that the article concluded that the Nigerian Baptists need to do more to their contributions to the political system to have more influence in the control of political power in Nigeria. The paper among many others recommended that Baptist clergies and leadership at all levels of governance in the Church such as Church, Association, Conference, and Convention levels should encourage their followers to join political parties and movements in their various constituencies and also be financial members, to aspire to hold key positions and also to do their best to contest various elective positions to be directly involved in the decision-making process in the governance of Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

The terms that need further clarification in this research work are: governance, politics, Baptist and secularist theory.

Governance

The concept of governance is generally understood to be mechanisms whereby an institution or organisation (be it the family, nation-state, or elements of it) incorporates the participation of relevant interest groups in defining the scope and content of its work-including the capacity to mediate among these interests when they enter into conflict and the means whereby it demonstrates accountability to those who support it through its mission mandates and the application of its resources in pursuit of its goals. The term “governance” can also be defined as the fundamental process by which the lives and dreams of a people are jointly pursued by deliberate and systematic strategies and policies for the attainment of their maximum potential. Likewise, governance means the combination of responsible leadership and enlightened public participation (Azeez, 2002). According to another perspective, the term “governance” is the method in which power is made use of in the management of a country’s social and economic resources for developmental purposes. In addition, governance is conceptualized and focuses on such issues as “the legitimacy of government”, accountability of political and official elements of government, the competence of governments to formulate policies and deliver services, respect for human rights, and the rule of law. Based on this analysis of governance, there are three distinctive aspects of governance. They are as follows: political regime structure, the process of exercising authority in the management of the

resources of the nation, economic and social resources, and the capacity of the government to design, formulate and implement policies as well as discharge or execute functions (Ojewumi, 2020). Similarly, a school of thought also defines governance as the exercise of economic, political, and administrative authority to manage a country's affairs at all levels. The scholars also believe that governance comprises mechanisms, processes, and institutions through which citizens and groups articulate their interests, exercise their legal rights, meet their obligations, and mediate their differences (Bassey and Ozumba, 2012).

Based on the above, what makes governance good relates to decisions that define expectations, grant power, or verify performance. Good governance involves either a separate process or a specific part of management or leadership processes (Grint, 1991). Furthermore, good governance has eight major characteristics which are: participatory, consensus, oriented, accountable, transparent, responsive, effective and efficient, equitable and inclusive, following the rule of law (Ayantayo, 2012). Likewise, good governance sustains and promotes equity based on the concept of non-discrimination to all. In good governance, there is evidence of participatory, transparent, judicious allocation of resources to address the collective problem confronting society, accountability, the rule of law, effectiveness, equity, and strategic vision (Gianluca, 2007).

Meanwhile, bad governance is defined as "The personalization of power, lack of human rights, endemic corruption and unelected and unaccountable government" (Weiss, n.d.). Moreover, to know whether the governance of a country is good or bad depends on the degree to which its institutions and processes are transparent and accountable to the people and how it allows them to participate in decisions that affect their lives. It is also the degree to which the private sector and organisations of civil society are free and able to participate (Shabbis and Maguire, 2002).

Politics

Politics has been considered to include all issues that concern the manner of the ordering or the organisation; in peace and war; of the affairs of societies and states. The making of the laws to guide men and society all comes as an important aspect of politics. Politics, according to Mbaeyi (1971), is also the greatest attribute of citizenship, as it enables or should enable men to have a say in the ordering of their affairs. All the thinking,

all the arguments, and all the discussion about the good of society and its affairs, whether done by an individual or in small or large groups and whether done openly or in private closets and clandestinely come within the province of politics.

In addition, politics can simply be referred to as the art and science of governance. It is a fact that every human being is a political being in one way or the other. Those who partake in active politics are the politicians (Yusuf, 2012). Furthermore, the term “politics” is generally applied to behaviour within civil governments, but politics has been observed in all human group interactions. It consists of social relations involving authority or power, the regulation of political units, and the methods and tactics used to formulate and apply social policy. Likewise, politics can also be seen as the set of activities that are associated with making decisions in groups or other forms of power relations between individuals, such as the distribution of resources or states. Moreover, politics is exercised on a wide range of social levels, from clans and tribes of traditional societies, through modern local governments, companies, and institutions up to sovereign states and the international level.

Baptist

Historically, there are at least two schools of thought that suggest reasons for the adoption of the name “Baptist”. The first school traced the origin to the Greek word “Baptizo” and the Latin “Baptista” that mean “dip” by way of immersion. The second school assumes that the Baptists got their name from John the Baptist, the forerunner of Jesus Christ, the first preacher to teach the doctrine to which the Baptists now hold (Ajayi, 2009). The fact is that the name comes from the Baptist practice of immersion. The people called “Baptists” were so named not by themselves but by their opponents. They were initially nicknamed “Anabaptist” – people that are advocating a second baptism.

In a like manner, the Baptists are protestant Christians who accept tenets of the Reformation namely: justification by faith, the authority of the scripture, the priesthood of the believer, and baptism of believers by immersion only (Ajayi, 2009). Furthermore, the Baptists teach that the Bible as against the tradition is the only source of faith and supreme authority of the church and the living church of Christ is composed only of regenerated or converted people, while baptism is only for regenerated

persons (only adults who have confessed Jesus Christ as their Lord and Saviour openly), these are persons who are spiritually mature enough to make an independent decision, that is; persons who have had personal experience of the Christian religion.

Likewise, a Baptist church is composed of a local congregation of baptised believers in Jesus Christ who voluntarily bond or join themselves together to carry out the work of Christ's repentance from sin and affirmation of faith in Jesus as Saviour and Lord as revealed in the authentically inspired word of God. This is in contrast to a state church in which all who are born within a given geographical territory and who receive the sacraments automatically become members or a church in which infants who are baptised are considered members (Ajayi, 2009).

The Nigerian Baptist Convention has its origins from the Foreign Mission Board of the Southern Baptist Convention (SBC) of the United States of America in 1850 (Ottuh and Thikan, 2015). The Nigerian Baptist Conventions (NBC) was officially formed in 1914 and the first convention was held at First Baptist Church, Idikan, Ibadan, Oyo state of Nigeria (Ajayi, 2009). According to Ajayi, "The mustard seed of Baptist work was planted in this land in 1850 by Revd. Thomas Jefferson Bowen, a missionary of the Foreign Mission Board of the Southern Baptist Convention, USA" (Ajayi, 2014).

Moreover, it is worthy of note that NBC provides as it has been doing since its inception for most Baptists in Nigeria a sense of belonging to a national Christian community. It remains a dynamic Christian organisation with continual growth in which churches and associations are added every year. The NBC is involved in spreading the faith and planting churches in Nigeria and beyond, in Africa, Europe and the USA. Theological education, liberal arts education, and leadership development are part of the ongoing activities. In addition, the Convention has established a university that was named after the Revd. Thomas Bowen, the pioneer Missionary of the denomination in Nigeria.

Secularism

Secularist theory separates religion and religious institutions from matters of the state. Therefore, the separation of religion and state is the foundation of secularism. This theory ensures religious groups do not interfere in the affairs of the state (Exploring Secularism). Furthermore, secularism deals

with the separation of religious institutions from state institutions and a public sphere where religion may participate, but not dominate. It is the freedom to practice one's faith or belief without harming others, or to change it or not depending on one's conscience. Moreover, secularism means equality of all citizens so that religious beliefs or lack of them do not put anyone at an advantage or a disadvantage (Exploring Secularism).

Nigerian Baptist Convention Perspective on Secularism and Politics

To start with, Ishola (2017) traces the origin of secularist theory to the United States of America through missionaries who brought the Gospel of Christ to Nigeria. Ishola is of the view that religious liberty serves as the cornerstone for the founding of the United States, and it is one of the key elements in the Constitution of the United States. The definition of religious liberty is embedded within and enshrined in the documents that became the First Amendment. It states as follows: "Congress shall make no law respecting an establishment of religion, or prohibiting the exercise thereof, or abridging the freedom of speech or of the press or the right of the people peaceably to assemble, and to petition the government for a redress of grievances. In summary, the separation of church and state according to Ishola is that government would not impose a state religion on all its citizens while the church would not want to dole out the government to carry out its sacred responsibilities. This means the state has no right to impose any law that is inimical to the well-being of the church, to infringe on the freedom of the church to govern itself as the Bible teaches. Neither would the state sponsor or allow any religion to have the upper hand over any other (Ishola, 2017). Likewise, the state is expected to provide freedom to all religions to exercise their rights and religious convictions and practices.

In addition, Ayokunle (2017) believes that separation of church and state does not mean that Baptists should not participate in politics and governance in their locale. Ayokunle's perspective is that the separation of church and state means that no government has the power to establish one religion as a state or to fund any religion from public funds (Ayokunle, 2017). Further to this, Ayokunle's view is that no state has the right to discriminate against one religion in favour of another such as the practice in some northern states of Nigeria where the Sharia legal system has been instituted in conformity with the belief that they are Islamic states. This means that both the church and the state are distinct (mutually exclusive);

one is not under the control of the other and one is not to usurp the rights and powers of the other (Ayokunle, 2017). It is therefore expected of the state to discharge its civil and political duties while the church is to discharge spiritual duties. This can be concluded that the church should stay out of the state's business and the state should stay out of the church's business.

Based on the two opinions above, it is worthy of note that the Baptist church believes that the state and the church cannot be fused because they have different purposes. The Baptist believes that the church's main responsibilities are to bring people to God, to advance the kingdom of God on earth, to give glory to God, to edify the saints and to do God's work in this sinful world. The state on the other hand, is meant to secure the lives and properties of her citizens, to provide amenities for the people, to defend the general interests of the citizens, and to be accountable to all irrespective of their religious affiliation. The Baptists believe that it will not augur well with the state and church if there is a fusion of relationships. They believe that whenever religion has power over the state or vice versa, both have been corrupted, and religious and civil liberties will suffer.

Summarily, Baptists reject a union or marriage between the two institutions by emphasizing religion as a personal relationship between the human soul and God, a relationship with which no one may interfere or stop. Therefore, the Baptist opinion on secularist theory can be seen in this form:

"The new principle of separation of church and state does not prohibit the involvement of Christians in public life, or that Baptists should not participate in politics or government in their country. Rather, what it means is that neither of the two should usurp the rights and powers of the other, that is, the church should not play the role of the state in matters of civil government and the state should not carry out the duties of the church in ecclesiastical matters. Indeed, Christians are encouraged to be involved in public life at every level but they must not seek to control the state. The essence is to water down the control or interference of states over religious affairs or over churches within their domain so as not to make such churches lose their focus or their prophetic functions. Thus, although Baptists believe that there will always be a relationship between the church and the state as they feel a responsibility to exert moral and spiritual influence on the latter;

they are nevertheless opposed to an official tie between the state and any religious organization” (Ajayi, 2009).

Though the Nigerian Baptist Convention has never prevented any member from taking an active part in political activities, once a member’s political interest is made known the church policy is that such member ceases to be a part of the church leadership or take any active role in the church leadership activities at any level whether at the local church, association, conference and Convention levels.

A good example to illustrate this fact is that of the Convention’s former General Secretary, Revd Dr Samuel Titilola Oladele Akande, who once contested the presidential primary election in Nigeria. According to Revd Dr S.T. Ola Akande, his resolve to venture into Nigerian politics bred him many opponents to his official assignments as the General Secretary of the NBC. He initially thought what was obtained in the USA where he was trained could be applicable in Nigeria also. In the USA, he argues that many Baptist clergies’ political beliefs had nothing to do with the spiritual leadership of their membership. Immediately, he made known his intention publicly, there was a lot of controversy in his religious constituency. He was advised to resign from his official duties as the NBC General Secretary, but he refused to be intimidated by these threats because he was not a man who can be easily subjugated by any sentiments, hero domination, or political or religious godfatherism. Dr Akande argued that his political affiliation was personal and cannot be hindered by any clause or human manipulation of any kind.

According to Emeritus Professor J. A. Ayoade in an oral interview, total separation of church and state does not exist. If anybody confronts the law of the state because he claims he is a Christian, he may spend the rest of his life in jail. So, the only way to get a state to behave in a Christian way is to have active Christian participation. For Christians to refuse that participation is a dereliction of Christian duties because it is a refusal to be the salt of the world. The professor of political science further states as follows:

“The Baptists are too rigid and even within the Christian cycle, the Baptists are still lacking. There are more Anglicans in public offices than there are Baptists. We denied ourselves prominence and by so doing, unconsciously we violated the great commission. When Obasanjo became Head of State as a military man, that was the first

time that a Baptist got national recognition. Rev. Dr. S.T. Ola Akande was his Pastor at Owu Baptist church, so when he became the head of state, he always invited Revd. S.T. Ola Akande to Dodan Barracks to preach. When he became the president in 1999, he appointed Revd. Prof Yusuf Ameh Obaje as the chaplain for Aso Rock Chapel. In politics, it is power that makes you powerful, you do not separate yourself from power. The Baptist has no strategy, it is rudderless. She has no vision to drive her mission. If you do not have a vision and you are talking about a mission, the mission cannot go because you have no vision. One of the things that is lacking in Baptists, is that we do not imbibe in our missions because we do not have a goal. So, the Baptists need to think more realistically and more scripturally to be able to make themselves worthwhile in the secular world and to be able to direct the world to eternity. Revd. S.T. Ola Akande's attempt to contest the presidency in the 1990s, was a bold step by a Baptist, but he did not get the support of the Baptists because the Baptists were not politically prepared or ready. Many Baptists ridiculed the attempt, so we lost that opportunity and our participation in the secular life must be put into higher gear so that we can be more relevant in the secular realm.”

In the perspective of another notable Baptist scholar, Prof Simon Ademola Ajayi of History Department, University of Ibadan, in an oral interview believed that an average Baptist in government is just like a typical Nigerian politician. It is difficult to assess them objectively because they have not made much impact on the political activities of Nigeria. There should therefore be encouragement at the levels of the local Church, Associations, Conferences and the Convention for Baptist politicians.

Similarly, another Baptist scholar, Dr. Adebimpe Olumide Aderounmu who is a Development Practitioner and Policy Researcher, in an oral interview, believed that politics is about power play, one thing people seek for in politics is power. What power does is seen in governance. Aderounmu believes that there is no single denomination in Christendom that is more politically trained than the Baptists because politics established Baptists. He argues that:

“Right from the sunbeam group, an average Baptist child has been trained to represent the congregation, not his family, not only to represent at the local level which may be community and town but in

associations comprising many communities, that representative is representing churches in his/her association. When it comes to marshalling your points, there is always issue, a Baptist has grown either through a process of representation of organ, or committed to present a report to the Executive Council (EC) or church-in-conference, as it were, where it could be approved or rejected depending on the relevance of such issue to development of the church and available resources. In that case, a Baptist member should be a good politician. Looking at what politics is all about, we should not waste the investment in an average Baptist member, in fact, they are needed in politics, who can challenge the President, and other principal officers in government without being rude or intimidated. That kind of boldness is what is needed in politics, and they are found more in an average Baptist than any other denomination that I have seen, that cannot be seen in many others. They (the Baptists) are always prepared. You are accountable in Baptist for your responsibility, so Baptists should get involved in politics because they have all it takes to be in politics.”

Roles and Contributions of the Nigerian Baptist Convention to the Governance in Nigeria

In the opinion of Revd. Dr. Dickson Madoghwe, in an oral interview, the Baptist's contribution to governance in Nigeria begins with training pastors in theological schools. He further states that the Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomosho and others give an all-round training, covering spiritual, moral, financial, political et cetera. Pastors are spiritually and ethically equipped to be good agents of the Convention and are also expected to demonstrate ethical values among the people of the society. Different church programmes, weekly preaching and Bible studies are done to help members to become good examples in the society. But Pastors who are interested in politics must resign from their pastorate because they should be pastors to all political affiliations. He also believes the Baptist Convention has done so much in mobilising members for politics and in sustaining governance in Nigeria.

Furthermore, another local church pastor, Rev. Dr. Tunji Taiwo, in an oral interview, believed that the Baptist authority has put some measures in place to checkmate erring Baptist politicians who are found wanting, and to

enhance their official performances in politics and governance in Nigeria. He says “Baptist involvement is to guide the people through prayer and counselling and also to monitor them in the areas of their professions. The church prays openly for those who are Baptist politicians. The Church charges them as her representatives knowing well that whatever they do makes the name of the church to be at stake. The church mobilises people to vote for the party of their choice. But if any church member is contending for an elective post, people will be mobilised to vote for him. The church also encourages members to register for and collect their permanent voter’s card to enable them vote during general elections.

Meanwhile, the Baptists have contributed to the sustainable governance in Nigeria through their various organs. For example, Christian Education Department of the Convention has done a lot in the adult literacy programme. The Social Ministries Department is known for the youths and widow’s empowerment, and training of the young graduates in learning a trade. The Health Ministry has many hospitals that cater to the health and well-being of Nigerians irrespective of their religious affiliations. Similarly, Baptists in Nigeria at all levels have schools that are doing well. The church has also invested in the university education with Bowen University that is cited in a Muslim-dominated area, Iwo, Osun state. All these and many others have contributed in no small measure to the sustainable governance in Nigeria.

Furthermore, when it comes to the Baptist contributions to the nation building and development in Nigeria, one important area where the Baptist relates to Nigerian society is in the raising of a new crop of elites. The Nigerian Baptist not only ran some of the institutions that produced the best-educated people in the country, but they also gave the products of such institutions opportunities for carrying greater responsibilities in the services of the mission and convention (Ajayi, 2010). Similarly, Baptists have contributed to producing men and women of distinction in various fields of human endeavour throughout the country from the inception of Baptist work, much more so, in recent times (Ajayi, 2010).³⁰ For example, in the political and legal scenes, the Baptists have figures like Dr. Mojola Agbebi, Nathaniel Oyerinde, Late Sage, Chief Obafemi Awolowo; Chief Samuel Ladoke Akintola, Chief Moshood Abiola; Chief Dr, Olusegun Obasanjo, Senator Abiola Ajimobi, Dr Peter Odili, Otunba Gbenga Daniel, Otunba Adebayo Akala; Dr. Emmanuel Uduaghan, Chief Olusegun Osoba,

and Senator Olorunnimbe Mamora. In addition, in the area of education, the Baptists have many distinguished scholars such as Professors J.A. Atanda, E.A Ayandele, Taiwo Okedara; Christianah Okedara, S. Ademola, Ajayi, John Ade Ajayi, Biola Odejide, Bisi Odejide, J.A. Ayoade, Dan Izebaye, J.A. Faniran, Tunji Olaopa, Ojetunji Aboyade, Bayo Okunade among many others. In the area of economics, the Baptists have Jacob Ajekiigbe, Tayo Aderinokun, Gamaliel Onosode, and many others.

Summarily, all these great Baptist men and women have contributed in no small measure to the sustainable governance and nation-building in Nigeria. Likewise, they have all proved to be people of substance with high level of integrity, uprightness and devotion, as well as service to God and humanity.

Conclusion

This paper has investigated the level of political involvements of the Baptists in Nigeria. For governance in Nigeria to be sustainable, the Baptist as a Christian denomination has roles to play. The Baptists should wake up from their political slumber and begin to take more active roles in the political system of Nigeria. They must not over practice the principles of secularism. They should become more active rather than being passive. All eligible Baptist voters should register for the election, be enlightened on the ideologies of different political parties and candidates, and also make efforts to vote for credible politicians. The leaders should be more vocal in expressing their view on all political and social matters. They should be ready to speak against any form of injustice, maladministration, corruption, nepotism, high-handedness, manipulation, and anything that can affect sustainable governance in Nigeria.

Finally, just like that of Deacon S.S. Iyanda, a Baptist who is an outstanding former board member of National Youth Service Corps (NYSC), a man of integrity who did not corrupt himself while in the active service of the federal government, every Baptist member in public and private offices should do likewise. The Baptists in public service should also develop integrity, truthfulness and godliness. The lifestyle of every Baptist should preach Christ they claim they are servicing so that through their moral uprightness and integrity, others from various Christian denominations and religious organisations can follow their examples.

Recommendations

In order for the Nigerian Baptists to have a better representation and impact in Nigerian politics and governance, this work will like to recommend as follows:

First, to enable Nigerian Baptists make progress and to be effective, they need to saturate the society with their political prowess. They must promote themselves politically. Their social ministry needs to be upgraded and improved upon. This is the linkage between their ministry and their social responsibilities. The Baptists are presently over-specialized in theology, while the Catholics are more politically vocal. The Nigerian Baptist theological institutions need to be restructured to allow a broader scope for the seminarians to have a deeper impact on the governance in Nigeria.

Second, the leaders of Baptist should be bold enough to contribute positively through the expression of their minds on Nigeria's national issues to register their participation in the governance of Nigeria. This will give them more recognition. They should also be fair while expressing their minds on national issues without sentiment.

Third, the church's leadership should mobilise resources to support people in politics for example, when Hon. Dwari George contested for the governor's seat in River State, he was found to be the best candidate. But he had little support to assist him in winning the election. The Baptist church contributed little or nothing. Baptist's governing body should always roll out various assistance to all their members who aspire to contest any elective post in the country.

Fourth, to support governance in Nigeria, the NBC should encourage better participation in politics. Also, the church should practice enviable corporate governance, practice of corporate social responsibilities even within the NBC membership. In addition, the Baptists should improve on their sustainable corporate social responsibilities by lending support to the poor and less privileged in society. This means they should engage in community activities to build an inclusive governance that the government can build upon.

Furthermore, the Baptists need to effectively support all 17 goals of the UN Sustainable Development Goals to build global partnership and collaboration. They should engage on these goals without leaving anyone behind. The Baptists for example need to do more in the health sector and

also to assist the poor in reducing the school fees to their higher institutions like Bowen University and theological colleges and seminaries.

Moreover, the Baptists should also do their best to put new programmes in place that will cater for many of their unemployed youths who are roaming about the streets of Nigeria. They need to improve their use of Information Communication Technology (ICT) to enable their youths to function well and compete adequately with their colleagues in other denominations and religions.

Finally, the church should encourage its members to vote, participate, and seek political offices because, from records, Baptist members have integrity. The church pastors should encourage their members to be actively involved in politics through prayers and weekly sermons.

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